

**MEASURING SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT: INTRODUCING
THE SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT INDEX (SED Index)****Yo'ldosheva Umida**

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Abstract. In today's world, social entrepreneurship is gaining more popularity and is becoming a necessary element of economic development. Nowadays, social entrepreneurship is becoming more important in the context of sustainable socio-economic development. This type of entrepreneurship is focused on creating positive social and economic impact aimed at eliminating inequalities, combating poverty and other problems, and promoting sustainable development. Based on the results of researches on sociodynamics and prospects of developing social entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, the article analyzes some methodologies to quantify the level of social entrepreneurship development within regions, followed by the proposal of a potential Social Entrepreneurship Development Index (SED Index) as an exemplary measurement tool.

Keywords: social entrepreneurship, factors impacting social entrepreneurship development, measuring the level of social entrepreneurship development within regions, Social Entrepreneurship Development Index (SED Index).

Annotatsiya. Hozirgi davrda ijtimoiy tadbirkorlikning dolzarbligi oshib va iqtisodiy rivojlanishning zaruriy elementiga aylanib bormoqda. Bugungi kunda ijtimoiy tadbirkorlik barqaror ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanish kontseptsiyasida yanada muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Tadbirkorlikning bu turi tengsizliklarni yo'qotishga, salbiy ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ta'sirni bartaraf etishga, qashshoqlik va boshqa muammolarga qarshi kurashishga va shu orqali barqaror rivojlanishga ko'maklashishga qaratilgan. Maqolada O'zbekistonda ijtimoiy tadbirkorlik sotsiodinamikasi va uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlar natijalari asosida, hududlarda ijtimoiy tadbirkorlikning rivojlanganlik darajasini o'lchash bo'yicha ba'zi metodologiyalar tahlil qilinib, namunaviy o'lchov vositasi sifatida Ijtimoiy Tadbirkorlikning Rivojlanganlik Darajasi Indeksi (ITRD Indeksi) taklif etilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: ijtimoiy tadbirkorlik, ijtimoiy tadbirkorlikning rivojlanirishga ta'sir etuvchi omillar, hududlarda ijtimoiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlanganlik darajasini o'lchash, Ijtimoiy tadbirkorlikning rivojlanganlik indeksi.

Аннотация. В современном мире социальное предпринимательство набирает все большую популярность и становится необходимым элементом экономического развития. В настоящее время социальное предпринимательство становится все более значимым в контексте устойчивого социально-экономического развития. Этот тип предпринимательства ориентирован на создание позитивного социального и экономического воздействия, направленного на устранение неравенства, борьбу с бедностью и насущными проблемами, а также на поощрение устойчивого развития. На основе результатов исследований социодинамики и перспектив развития социального предпринимательства в Узбекистане в статье проанализированы некоторые методики оценки уровня развития социального предпринимательства в регионах с последующим предложением потенциального Индекса Развития Социального Предпринимательства в качестве примерного инструмента измерения.

Ключевые слова: социальное предпринимательство, факторы, влияющие на развитие социального предпринимательства, измерение уровня развития социального предпринимательства в регионах, Индекс Развития Социального Предпринимательства.

Introduction

Uzbekistan today is at a new stage of its development, where large-scale political, administrative, economic and social reforms are taking place. These circumstances make it necessary to consider a variety of tools for managing social processes and effectively solving social problems.

The problem of integrating the processes of economic and social sustainability is becoming important. Such orientation of socio-economic development and the main tasks are defined in the Strategy "Uzbekistan-2030" [1], in the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026[2], Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 20.10.2018 No. 841 "On measures for the implementation of national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development for the period up to 2030"[3] and many other regulatory legal acts.

Social entrepreneurship is one of the effective tools for achieving socio-economic stability. As a relatively new and innovative phenomenon, it contributes to the growth of the level and quality of life of the population, increasing the competitiveness and efficiency of the economy, which is very relevant right now in the light of the crisis in the global economy and the slowdown in economic growth due to the pandemic.

In Uzbekistan, great attention has recently been paid to the integration of the processes of economic sustainability and social stability, but there is still a lack of systematic scientific research aimed at formulating proposals for the effective use of social entrepreneurship as one of the most effective tools for achieving socio-economic stability. Socio-economic studies of the essence, dynamics and prospects for the development of social entrepreneurship are necessary to create an empirical base for forecasting the vectors of development of the national economy and the social sphere. To effectively support the growth of social entrepreneurship, it becomes crucial to have a comprehensive measurement tool that can assess its development in different regions. This article proposes the development of a Potential Social Entrepreneurship Development Index (SED Index) based on an analysis of social entrepreneurship development in Uzbekistan and expert opinions on the key factors that contribute to its growth in a region.

Methodology

Within the framework of our research one of the objectives was to develop a robust measurement tool, the SED Index, which can be used to assess the development of social entrepreneurship in mahallas/ regions of Uzbekistan in future. There is no organizational legal form as "social enterprise" in Uzbekistan or any legal regulatory framework for social entrepreneurship. We could only make an analysis of socially oriented business and conduct expert interviews. A panel of experts comprising individuals with extensive experience in the field of social innovations, economics, political economy, CSR, entrepreneurship and NGOs was consulted. Through structured interviews and focused group discussions, their insights were gathered regarding the main factors necessary for social entrepreneurship development in a region. The experts were selected based on their expertise, knowledge, and practical understanding of social entrepreneurship ecosystems. Case study analysis was conducted in Scandinavian countries (Norway, Sweden, Denmark). This involved studying successful social enterprises, examining their growth trajectories, and identifying the key factors that played a crucial role in their development. Data was collected through interviews, surveys, and observation of various social entrepreneurship initiatives. Based on the findings from the case study analysis and expert opinions, a comprehensive list of factors influencing social entrepreneurship development was

compiled. These factors included legal frameworks, access to finance, networking opportunities, support services, market conditions, and community engagement, among others. The experts participated in a survey to rank the factors in terms of their importance, which were then weighed accordingly. The SED Index based on the findings of the analysis and expert inputs was constructed.

Findings and results

Analyzing the results of case studies and in-depth expert interviews in the Scandinavian countries and Uzbekistan, the following observations can be made regarding the coincidence of answers for each aspect, which experts and respondents noted as important for the development or sustainability of social entrepreneurship:

Enactment of the Law on Social Entrepreneurship:

- In Uzbekistan, this aspect turned out to be more important than in the Nordic countries (92.59 % respondents compared to 65% in the Scandinavian countries), indicating that there is a greater need to create a legislative framework to support social entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan.

Separate legal form:

- Both regions attach great importance to this aspect, but the Scandinavian countries noted it slightly more important (95% of respondents compared to 92.59% in Uzbekistan). This indicates that both countries recognize the need for a separate organizational and legal form that takes into account the specifics of social entrepreneurship.

Awareness-raising:

- In Uzbekistan, this aspect was noted as important by all interviewees (100%), which indicates the need for information and education in the field of social entrepreneurship. In the Scandinavian countries, this aspect was also rated highly (75%), but not as much as in Uzbekistan.

Financial support:

- Both regions attached great importance to financial support for social entrepreneurs. In Uzbekistan, this aspect was noted by 92.59% of respondents, and in the Scandinavian countries - 90%.

Tax benefits:

- In Uzbekistan, tax incentives were estimated slightly higher than in the Scandinavian countries (81.48% vs. 60%). This may indicate the need to create more favorable tax conditions for the development of social entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan.

Training:

- Both regions assess training as one of the important aspects for the development of social entrepreneurship. In Uzbekistan, this aspect was noted by all respondents (100%), and in the Scandinavian countries - 85%.

Platform networking and motivation:

- Both aspects (platform networking and motivation) were assessed at approximately the same level in both countries. In Uzbekistan, approximately 81.48% of respondents noted the importance of these aspects, and in the Scandinavian countries, 95%.

Public Recognition:

- In Uzbekistan, this aspect was rated higher (85.19% of respondents compared to 55% of respondents in the Nordic countries), which may indicate the greater importance of recognition and support of social entrepreneurs by society in Uzbekistan.

Investment:

- In Uzbekistan, investments were slightly higher than in the Scandinavian countries

(62.96% compared to 60% in the Scandinavian countries).

Based on these findings and studies several indexes that measure the development of social entrepreneurship in specific regions or countries such as the Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI), the European Social Entrepreneurship Monitor (ESEM), the Ashoka Social Financial Services Index, the African Social Entrepreneurship Index (ASEI), the SED Index was constructed. The SED Index was constructed by assigning numerical values to each factor based on their relative significance.

Indicator	1. Number of Social Enterprises:	2. Social Impact Measurement:	3. Funding and Investment:	4. Regulatory Framework:	5. Collaboration and Networking:	6. Education and Training:	7. Support Ecosystem:
Score definition	Score Definition: - 1-3: Very low number of social enterprises in the region,	Score Definition: - 1-3: Limited ability of social enterprises to measure	Score Definition: - 1-3: Limited availability of financial resources for social	Score Definition: - 1-3: Weak or non-existent supportive regulator	Score Definition: - 1-3: Low level of collaboration and networking among social enterprises	Score Definition: - 1-3: Limited provision of education and training	Score Definition: - 1-3: Weak presence of support organizations and infrastruc

	<p>indicating low interest and activity in social entrepreneurship. - 4-6: Moderate number of social enterprises in the region, indicating some level of interest and activity in social entrepreneurship. - 7-10: High number of social enterprises in the region, indicating strong interest and activity in social entrepreneurship.</p>	<p>and report their social impact, indicating low transparency and accountability. - 4-6: Some ability of social enterprises to measure and report their social impact, indicating moderate transparency and accountability. - 7-10: Effective ability of social enterprises to measure and report their social impact, indicating high transparency</p>	<p>entrepreneurship activities in the region, including few grants, loans, and impact investment opportunities. - 4-6: Moderate availability of financial resources for social entrepreneurship activities in the region, including some grants, loans, and impact investment opportunities. - 7-10: Wide availability of financial resources for social entrepreneurship</p>	<p>within the framework for social entrepreneurship in the region, lacking legal structures, tax incentives, and policy measures. - 4-6: Some supportive regulatory frameworks for social entrepreneurship in the region, with limited legal structures, tax incentives, and policy measures. - 7-10: Strong and effective supportive regulatory</p>	<p>within the region, with minimal presence of networks, associations, and platforms. - 4-6: Moderate level of collaboration and networking among social enterprises within the region, with some presence of networks, associations, and platforms. - 7-10: High level of collaboration and networking among social enterprises within the region, facilitated by well-established networks, associations, and platforms.</p>	<p>opportunities for social entrepreneurs in the region, including few courses, workshops, and mentoring programs. - 4-6: Some provision of education and training opportunities for social entrepreneurs in the region, including a moderate number of courses, workshops, and mentoring programs. - 7-10: Ample provision</p>	<p>ure for social entrepreneurship in the region, including limited availability of incubators, accelerators, and consultation services. - 4-6: Some presence of support organizations and infrastructure for social entrepreneurship in the region, including a moderate availability of incubators, accelerators, and consultation services. - 7-10: Strong and effective presence of support</p>
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		ncy and accounta bility.	eurship activities in the region, including multiple grants, loans, and impact investme nt opportuni ties.	y framework ks for social entrepren eurship in the region, including well-establishe d legal structures , tax incentive s, and policy measures.		of education and training opportuni ties for social entrepren eurs in the region, including a wide range of courses, workshop s, and mentorin g programs .	organizati ons and infrastru ct ure for social entreprene urship in the region, including well-establishe d incubators , accelerato rs, and consultati on services.
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* Methodology for Index of Social Entrepreneurship Development (ISED)

Discussion

The development of a Potential Social Entrepreneurship Development Index (SED Index) holds great promise for assessing and quantifying the growth of social entrepreneurship in various regions. The SED Index serves as a valuable tool to measure social entrepreneurship development in a region. By applying the index to various regions, policymakers, researchers, and practitioners can gain insights into the strengths and weaknesses of each area, thereby facilitating targeted interventions and policy formulation. The findings of this study provide a basis for understanding the factors that contribute to the growth of social entrepreneurship, which can guide the design and implementation of support programs and initiatives.

However, it is important to acknowledge the existing limitations that hinder the immediate measurement of social entrepreneurship development. One major challenge is the lack of a regulatory framework and the absence of a recognized legal form for social enterprises in certain regions. Without a standardized definition and structure for social enterprises, it becomes difficult to gather accurate data and measurements. Additionally, the absence of mechanisms for collecting data specifically on social entrepreneurship further complicates the measurement process.

Conclusion

While these barriers currently impede the full implementation of the SED Index, it is crucial to emphasize that, with the introduction of appropriate regulatory frameworks and mechanisms for data gathering, regions can effectively measure their social entrepreneurship development levels. It is imperative for policymakers, stakeholders, and researchers to work collaboratively in establishing supportive legal frameworks, defining social enterprise structures, and implementing comprehensive data collection systems. As such, this study serves as a

foundation for future research and policy discussions, highlighting the importance of addressing these impediments and taking proactive steps towards enabling accurate measurement of social entrepreneurship development. By adopting the SED Index in regions that have implemented the necessary measures, policymakers can gain valuable insights into the effectiveness of their initiatives and identify areas for improvement. Ultimately, by addressing the challenges outlined and embracing the potential of the SED Index, regions can actively foster the growth of social entrepreneurship. This, in turn, will contribute to the creation of sustainable social impact, economic development, and positive transformation in our communities.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 12.09.2023. № PD-158 on Strategy «Uzbekistan-2030» – www.lex.uz
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 28.01.2022. № PD-60 on Strategy of Development of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 – www.lex.uz
3. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 20.10.2018 No. 841 "On measures for the implementation of national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development for the period up to 2030"– www.lex.uz
4. Drayton W. The citizen sector: Becoming as entrepreneurial and competitive as business / W. Drayton // California Management Review, 2002. №44 (3). P. 120-132.
5. Martin R.L., Osberg S. Social Entrepreneurship: The Case for Definition / R.L. Martin // Stanford Social Innovation Review. Spring, 2007. P.29-39.
6. Mawson A. The Social Entrepreneur: Making Communities Work / A. Mawson// Atlantic Books, 2008.
7. Nardo, M., Saisana, M., Saltelli, A., Tarantola, S., Hoffman, A., Giovannini, E., & Funtowicz, S. (2005). Handbook on constructing composite indicators: Methodology and user guide. OECD Publishing.
8. Smith, D. J., Steen, J., Hartman, E. V., & Muller, C. (2018). Social entrepreneurship in the policy context: A comparative analysis of rural social enterprise ecosystems in Latin America. Entrepreneurship & Regional Development, 30(1-2), 80-102.